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Policy Brief 2026/03
March 23, 2026
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EU Pharmaceutical Law Reform: Addressing Delays and Unequal Access to Medicines

Issue/Problem

On March 6, 2026, the European Union published its pharmaceutical law reforms, targeting legislation that has remained largely unchanged for over two decades. The reforms attempt to balance making the EU the most “attractive and competitive hub for research and innovation by 2030” while improving access for patients across Member States.

Description of the Problem

The current framework does not ensure that medicines approved at the EU level are actually available in all countries. Companies choose where to launch their products and often prioritize more profitable markets. This leads to significant differences in access: on average, patients in Germany can access new medicines in about 133 days, while in Romania delays can exceed 800 days. In some countries, medicines are not launched at all. For example, CAR-T cancer therapies, although approved by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in 2018, remain unavailable in 26% of European countries. At the same time, there are growing concerns that pharmaceutical companies are shifting investment away from the EU towards more attractive markets, such as the United States and China. While Europe accounted for 55% of new medicines in the 1970s compared to 31% in the United States, in 2024, 79% of new medicines approved by both the FDA and EMA were approved in the United States first.

Results

To make the EU more attractive to companies, the reform aims to streamline complex administrative processes and shorten the EMA’s evaluation period from 210 days to 180 days. It also allows new medicines to benefit from extended regulatory protection of up to 11 years, subject to conditions such as addressing unmet medical needs, exceeding the United States’ standard 5-year data exclusivity for small-molecule drugs. To improve access across the EU, a new Article 56a would also allow EU countries to oblige companies to supply protected medicines in quantities that meet patient needs. If adopted, the following two years will serve as a transition period.

Lessons Learned

Canada faces similar concerns to that of the EU over drug development and access. The success or failure of the EU actions will provide meaningful insight into how Canada will be able to influence company launch strategies and investments.